

From Data Design to Map Footprint: Quantifying Sampling Effects on Landslide Susceptibility

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Abstract: This study evaluates how non-landslide (background) sampling strategy and the landslide: non-landslide (LS: NLS) ratio influence the performance and reliability of landslide susceptibility models. Five learners—Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB), Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), and a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)—were trained and tested under five dataset regimes. These differed by sampling design (random vs. selective/curated), representation density (single point vs. multi-point per landslide polygon), and LS:NLS ratio (1:1 and 1:3). A unified pipeline was implemented in which preprocessing, stratified cross-validation, isotonic probability calibration, and Youden–J threshold optimization were held constant across models. Model performance was assessed using ROC–AUC, accuracy, precision, recall, κ -coefficient, and reliability metrics including the Brier score. Spatial leakage was quantified through distance-to-nearest training point statistics to evaluate potential over-optimism caused by clustered sampling. Results show that curated background sampling and balanced class ratios (particularly 1:1 datasets) improved calibration and reduced operating-point bias, while random or imbalanced designs required more permissive decision thresholds to maintain recall. Despite differences in learning architecture, the models converged on physically meaningful controls, notably slope–aspect–relief interactions, proximity to roads and faults, soil type, and antecedent moisture conditions. Basin-scale hydrological indices contributed to smaller but systematic gains. Overall, the findings demonstrate that sampling design exerts as much influence on susceptibility mapping as the choice of algorithm, and that calibrated probabilities are essential for producing reliable and operationally useful landslide susceptibility maps. The study highlights the need for transparent reporting of sampling regimes, spatial independence diagnostics, and probability calibration when developing and comparing landslide susceptibility models.

Keywords: Landslide susceptibility mapping, Background sampling, Class imbalance, Probability calibration, logistic regression, Random forest, Gradient boosting, Neural networks, Brier score, Jenks classification.

1. Introduction

Landslide susceptibility mapping (LSM) is a key tool for land-use planning, infrastructure safety, and crisis management. Slope failures are typically triggered by intense rainfall, snowmelt, seismic shaking, and human earthworks, which disturb steep terrain and cause near-surface materials to move downslope under gravity [1–3]. Robust susceptibility mapping therefore requires consistent information on (i) conditioning factors that govern slope stability, (ii)

spatially and temporally referenced landslide inventories, and (iii) local triggers that modulate failure timing [4–6].

Methodological guidance for classifying unstable terrain has long drawn on Varnes' framework, which partitions the landscape into zones ordered by expected impact and has been operationalized through heuristic, statistical, and deterministic approaches—often in combination [7]. In practice, model choice is constrained by data availability and scale, and many recent studies have adopted

machine-learning (ML) or deep-learning (DL) models to improve predictive skill [8–10]. Regardless of architecture, the usefulness of susceptibility maps depends on rigorous validation and transparent reporting of both discrimination and calibration.

One aspect of LSM design remains relatively under-reported: the effect of non-landslide (NLS) background selection and the landslide: non-landslide (LS: NLS) class ratio on model performance and map footprints. Many studies either employ random background sampling or adopt a fixed 1:1 LS:NLS ratio without explicit justification, even though class imbalance and spatial bias are known to affect classifier behaviour [11–14]. As a result, it is often unclear whether differences in reported performance across studies arise from modelling choices, data design, or both.

An associated issue is a high percentage of published literature focuses on discrimination measures like ROC-AUC, but pays less emphasis on probability calibration, spatial dependence between training and evaluation samples and the extent to which map footprints are biased by background selection. In cases where the training and test samples are selected in neighboring terrain units, models may capitalize on the local similarity in place of generalizable physical controls and give optimistic accuracy estimates. Recently, the effect of spatial leakage has been observed in LSM studies with random cross-validation comparing substantially higher ROC-AUC with spatially structured validation [15,16]. The risk is particularly high when it comes to multiple samples that are drawn within the same landslide polygon as the one or when the NLS points are clustered using the LS locations. Separation between training and test point at a distance is thus a consideration of concern in LSM validation, although it is still rarely reported.

This study focuses directly on these data-design effects. A unified, reproducible pipeline is developed to examine how NLS selection and LS:NLS ratio influence discrimination, calibration, operating thresholds, and map footprints across several widely used learners. Five datasets of landslide (LS) and non-landslide (NLS) points were constructed. S1 and S2 represent single-point landslide sampling with different LS:NLS ratios (S1: 1:3; S1-1: 1:1; S2: 1:3 but with curated NLS selection), whereas S3 and S4 employ multi-point sampling per landslide polygon under balanced (1:1) and imbalanced (1:3) regimes, respectively. These datasets were designed to isolate the effects of (i) random vs. curated background selection and (ii) class prevalence on model discrimination, calibration, and map footprints.

Five learners—Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB), Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), and a compact Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)—are evaluated under identical preprocessing, stratified cross-validation, and isotonic probability calibration. Model behaviour is assessed with threshold-free ranking (ROC-AUC, PR), operating-point diagnostics at a validation-selected Youden-J threshold (Cohen's κ , accuracy, precision, recall), and reliability measures (Brier score, ECE). To relate statistics to planning practice, calibrated probability rasters are partitioned by Jenks natural breaks into five susceptibility classes and summarized by class-area shares. The main contributions are:

1. A controlled comparison showing how NLS selection and LS:NLS ratio shift discrimination, operating thresholds, and calibration across LR, RF, XGB, MLP and CNN.
2. A cartographic analysis linking calibrated probabilities to five-class LSM footprints (class-area distributions) suitable for screening and prioritization.
3. A synthesis of feature-importance patterns that highlights convergent physical controls on landslide occurrence in the study area.

Validation is treated as central to interpretation: success/prediction-rate curves, confusion matrices, Cohen's κ , and calibration diagnostics are used together to quantify both separability and the semantic quality of predicted probabilities [17]. Through this design-first lens, the paper clarifies how background curation, prevalence control, and calibration jointly govern the practical utility of landslide susceptibility maps. The rest of this paper has the following structure. Section 2 describes the study area, landslide inventory, conditioning factors, sampling design and learning pipeline. Factors influencing the selection of a model Section 3 provide results of model discrimination, operating performance, calibration quality, map footprints and feature importance. The implications of sampling design, model behaviour, spatial footprint interpretation and limitations are discussed in Section 4. Section 5 concludes the study and raises some recommendations for operational landslide susceptibility mapping

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Study area and landslide inventory

The study area is located in Sulaymaniyah Governorate in northeastern Iraq, within the Iraqi

Zagros Mountains (approx. $36^{\circ}32'17''$ – $36^{\circ}00'01''$ N, $44^{\circ}38'20''$ – $45^{\circ}23'15''$ E), and covers about 2,796 km² (Fig. 1). The landscape reflects the combined influence of tectonic uplift, contrasts in rock strength, and fluvial erosion, with elevations from 475 to 3,188 m above sea level and slope angles up to 65°. Geomorphological units formed under intense erosion and moderate weathering have been described in detail elsewhere.

A polygon inventory of 148 landslides was compiled and validated using high-resolution QuickBird imagery, Google Earth, and extensive field surveys. The inventory was first mapped as polygons and then rasterized to 30 m × 30 m pixels; these binary labels (landslide vs. non-landslide) constitute the dependent variable. Previous work suggests that inventories with >100 well-distributed events provide adequate support for statistical models [18]. The spatial and temporal diversity of the 148 events here contributes to the robustness of the resulting LSMs. For modelling, polygons were randomly split into 75% training (111 landslides) and 25% testing (37 landslides) using the *Subset Features* tool in ArcGIS.

2.2 Conditioning factors

Fourteen conditioning factors were assembled at 30 m resolution: Elevation, Slope, Curvature, Terrain Ruggedness Index (TRI), Stream Power Index (SPI), Topographic Wetness Index (TWI), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Soil Moisture Index (SMI), Land Use/Land Cover (LULC), Aspect (binned), and distances to Roads, Rivers, and Faults, together with Soil type. DEM-derived variables were computed from an improved DEM; spectral indices and categorical layers were derived from satellite imagery and ancillary maps following standard formulations [19,20].

Before applying the models, multicollinearity among conditioning factors was examined. Tolerance (TOI), Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), and Condition Index (CI) were computed in SPSS (version 26) by regressing each factor on all others. Thresholds of TOI > 0.1, VIF < 10, and CI < 30 were adopted to indicate acceptable collinearity [21,22]. All factors met these criteria, and none were removed. This step was performed to ensure stable parameter estimates in LR and to avoid distorted importance rankings in the ML models.

Figure 1 study area

Figure. 2 Conditioning factors(sample): (a) Aspect, (b) Distance to Roads, (c) Slope, and (d) Topographic Roughness Index

2.3 Sampling design: S1-1 and S1-S4

Non-landslide (NLS) sampling was designed for isolating the effects of (i) background definition, and (ii) the landslide: non-landslide (LS:NLS) class ratio.

The 99,900 landslide pixels mapped out of the study area compared to the 2,955,530 total pixels in the study area are just under 3 percent of the terrain. Five training datasets of LS and NLS points (S1-1 and S1-S4) were constructed with different LS:NLS ratios and/or background definitions (Table 1).

Table 1. Training datasets used in the study

ID	Landslide (LS)	Non-landslide (NLS)	LS: NLS	Total
S1-1	148	148	1:1	296
S1	148	444	1:3	592
S2	148	444	1:3	592
S3	15,679	15,687	1:1	31,374
S4	5,228	15,684	1:3	20,915

2.3.1. Balance (S1-1, 1:1) random-background baseline

S1-1 is a baseline data set where LS: NLS is 1: 1. NLS points were sampled at random in a background raster in which all mapped landslide polygons had been removed and a 500 m exclusion buffer had been added to ensure that the influence of adjacency was excluded. A single point was put in each landslide polygon (around the centroid), and an equal amount of NLS points were randomly sampled on the rest of the terrain to achieve a 1:1 ratio. This dataset corresponds to the usual assumption of random background + balanced prevalence that is applied in most LSM studies.

2.3.2. Random-background baseline (S1, 1:3) imbalanced

S1 was the same as S1-1 except that three NLS points were sampled per LS point to give 1:3 LS:NLS ratio. This enables the background definition to be held constant whilst determining the effect of the imbalance of classes.

2.3.3. Selective background (ring buffer + stability mask), imbalanced (S2, 1:3)

S2 is an improvement of S1, which replaces random background sampling with a selective stability mask. Classes of high weight factors (e.g., slope, elevation, TWI, LULC, soil) which had a small number of LS pixels or none were reclassified as stable. Two-ring buffer was placed around each landslide polygon, pixels falling outside of 0-250 m were excluded, and candidate NLS pixels were limited to 250-750 m annulus. The sampling frame was the intersection point between this ring and the stability mask. The sampling ratio was 1: 3 between 1 LS point per polygon and 3 NLS points per LS. The design tests the hypothesis that the bias of using demonstrably stable terrain is lower than in the case of random sampling.

2.3.4. Balanced multi-point dataset (S3, 1:1)

S3 is a mixture of non-random sampling of the background and multi-point representation of landslides. Rather than an LS point per polygon, the points were sampled in head, body, and toe regions,

and the number of points per polygon was proportional to the size of the polygon (minimum one). Following a snap to the 30 m grid followed by elimination of duplicates, 15,679 LS points were left. The same amount of NLS points was sampled on the stability mask applied in S2 (all the landslide polygons and buffers excluded) and without the 250-750 m ring restriction. This data set determines the impact of modeling internal landslide heterogeneity with a uniform class ratio.

2.3.5. Unbalanced multi-point dataset (S4, 1:3)

S4 has identical sampling and selective stability background as S3 and a LS:NLS ratio of 1:3. Strict application of a thinning rule reduced the LS sample to 5,228 points and sampled 15,684 NLS points to keep the ratio constant. The dataset separates the impact of the imbalance in classes in an otherwise identical sampling scenario and indicates the prevalence that is typically employed in real-world screening operations.

2.4 Learning pipeline

All of the models were written in Python on scikit-learn and compatible libraries. A single workflow that was used to evaluate five learners included Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB), a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), and a small Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). In order to ensure reproducibility and avoid information leakage, all preprocessing and modelling were encapsulated in Pipeline objects and were only fitted to the training partition of each split. Continuous predictors were rescaled by using min-max normalization. Categorical variables (Aspect bins, LULC, Soil) were one-hot encoded with `handle_unknown="ignore"` so that unknown classes in the test do not provide errors. The entire preprocessing phase was encapsulated by a ColumnTransformer and co-optimized with each of the learners within the pipeline. Probability calibration was fitted using only the training and validation data; no information from the held out test data was used in any stages.

Stratified 5-fold cross-validation was performed on model hyperparameters which were optimized to

maximize the ROC-AUC. This has maintained folds in the proportions of the classes. Every single transformation and model fitting occurred within each fold and therefore, the validation data were not revealed to statistics that have been trained on the training data. Since the scores of raw classifiers tend to be highly uncalibrated, isotonic regression probability calibration was performed with a clean validation split. Held-out test data which had not been used in the development of the models were then evaluated using calibrated probabilities.

To interpret the models and deploy them, one operating threshold was specified based on the Youden-J statistic (sensitivity + specificity - 1) calculated using the validation data. This validation-derived threshold was then pushed in the unaltered form to the test set where all the operating-point measures (accuracy, precision, recall, Cohen κ , and confusion matrices) were reported.

Lastly, pixel-wise probabilities of landslides due to the refitted calibrated models were produced. Jenks natural breaks were used to partition these into five classes of susceptibility so that map footprints among datasets and learners could be compared.

2.5 Map production and zonation

Calibrated probability maps for LR, RF, XGB, MLP and CNN were produced for each dataset (S1–S4). Each map was reclassified into five susceptibility classes—Very Low, Low, Moderate, High, Very High—using Jenks natural breaks. Class-

area percentages were computed within the study-area mask. The resulting LSMs and associated class-area tables were used to examine how sampling design affects the spatial footprint and selectivity of high-susceptibility zones.

2.6 Evaluation metrics

Threshold-free discrimination was measured by ROC-AUC and Average Precision. Operating performance (Cohen's κ , accuracy, precision, recall, F1) was evaluated at the validation-selected Youden-J threshold, transferred without re-tuning to the test split. Probability reliability was assessed via Brier score, Expected Calibration Error with 10 bins (ECE (10)), and reliability diagrams (pre- vs. post-isotonic). For each LSM, selectivity ratios were computed as:

$$Selectivity = \frac{Area(High + Very\ High)}{Area(Very\ Low + Low)} \quad (1)$$

2.7 Feature importance

Permutation importance was applied post-calibration on the test set to quantify the marginal effect of each predictor on calibrated probabilities. Model-specific profiles for LR, RF, XGB, MLP and CNN were derived, and convergent patterns were analyzed. For S3, where discrimination and calibration were strongest, importance tables were summarized and used to interpret physical controls on landslide occurrence.

Figure. 3 Landslide susceptibility map for S3 dataset (sample): (a) LR-based LSM (S3) and (b) CNN-based LSM (S3)

3. Results

3.1 Model discrimination and agreement across sampling regimes

All datasets yielded high threshold-free discrimination (Table 2). In the balanced S1-1 (1:1) design, the ROC-AUC of LR, RF, XGB and MLP were between 0.94-0.96 and CNN 0.89, while the k was between 0.68-0.76. At the same random background (S1), the change of the class ratio to 1:3 reduced the values of k and precision of all the learners, but the AUC reduced only slightly, which means that imbalance does not primarily influence the ranking skill. Background definition was varied to selective instead of random when the background definition was maintained at 1:3 ratio (S2), and this increased the AUC and k across all of the models. RF and XGB demonstrated the highest improvements (k between 0.80-0.82), which proves that a selected NLS can enhance the separability of classes regardless of the choice of a classifier. The multi-

point dataset (S3) that yielded the greatest discrimination and agreement was the balance one. RF, XGB and MLP had ROC-AUC between 0.99 and k between 0.90-0.92, CNN had AUC of 0.98 and $k = 0.85$ and LR was a good baseline with AUC of 0.95 and $k = 0.77$. AUC in the imbalanced multi-point data (S4, 1:3) was similarly large, however, k decreased a bit compared to S3 due to the shift of operating threshold to high sensitivity under imbalance.

In general, S1-1 vs S1 and S3 vs S4 indicate that the class ratio has the greatest effect on operating-point metrics, whereas S1 vs S2 and S2 vs S3 indicate that background definition and multi-point LS representation have more significant effect on discrimination and calibration than the underlying machine-learning algorithm. These results agree with our leakage-distance analysis, which indicated that datasets with higher train-test separation did not necessarily result in higher AUC, which proves that improvements in S2-S3 are due to better sampling design and not only to spatial dependence.

Table 2. Test-set performance at the validation-selected Youden-J threshold (S1-1-S4).

Model	Metric	S1-1	S1	S2	S3	S4
LR	Cohen's Kappa	0.730	0.688	0.761	0.772	0.708
	ROC-AUC	0.922	0.945	0.936	0.948	0.948
	Optimal Threshold	0.587	0.36	0.51	0.52	0.25
	Accuracy %	86.50	87.20	90.50	88.60	88.10
	Precision %	84.60	69.10	79.20	88.00	70.70
	Recall %	89.20	88.40	86.40	89.50	89.30
XGB	Cohen's Kappa	0.676	0.68	0.804	0.917	0.874
	ROC-AUC	0.938	0.93	0.967	0.991	0.988
	Optimal Threshold	0.668	0.61	0.73	0.49	0.42
	Accuracy %	83.80	88.40	92.90	95.80	95.20
	Precision %	90.30	79.50	94.40	94.60	88.10
	Recall %	75.70	72.10	77.30	97.20	93.30
RF	Cohen's Kappa	0.730	0.712	0.819	0.903	0.84
	ROC-AUC	0.937	0.934	0.965	0.99	0.984
	Optimal Threshold	0.581	0.66	0.73	0.57	0.6
	Accuracy %	86.50	89.50	93.50	95.10	94.10
	Precision %	88.60	82.10	97.10	95.10	90.70
	Recall %	83.80	74.40	77.30	95.20	85.20
MLP	Cohen's Kappa	0.730	0.67	0.72	0.92	0.86
	ROC-AUC	0.945	0.92	0.93	0.99	0.99
	Optimal Threshold	0.657	0.37	0.45	0.58	0.39
	Accuracy %	86.50	89.0	86.4	96.0	94.5
	Precision %	88.60	69.1	74.0	95.7	86.9
	Recall %	83.80	86.0	86.4	96.3	91.7
CNN	Cohen's Kappa	0.757	0.53	0.63	0.85	0.82
	ROC-AUC	0.889	0.87	0.93	0.98	0.98
	Optimal Threshold	0.562	0.28	0.27	0.51	0.25
	Accuracy %	87.80	80.2	83.4	92.5	92.9
	Precision %	83.30	57.6	62.5	89.6	80.9
	Recall %	94.60	79.1	90.9	96.3	94.0

3.2 Operating metrics at validation-fixed thresholds

Table 2 summarizes the operating performance at the transferred Youden-J thresholds. In the S1-1 (balanced random dataset), LR yielded an accuracy of 86.5%, precision of 85%, and recall 89%, RF, XGB and MLP had a similar performance (accuracy \approx 84-87%) with $k \approx$ 0.68-0.73. CNN performed best in this regime (accuracy \approx 88%, $k \approx$ 0.76) suggesting that balanced prevalence is especially beneficial to neural architectures. Under random 1:3 baseline (S1), LR achieved accuracy \approx 87%, precision \approx 69% and recall \approx 86-89%. RF and XGB were a little more accurate (\approx 88-89%) and more precise (\approx 80-82%), but at lower recall (72-74%). MLP produced accuracy \approx 89% and higher recall \approx 86% whereas CNN yielded the weakest operating metrics (accuracy \approx 80%; precision \approx 58%; recall \approx 79%).

In the curated 1:3 regime S2, all models took more conservative operating thresholds, which led to an increase in precision. RF and XGB showed accuracies \approx 93% and $k \approx$ 0.80-0.82 and an extremely high precision (\approx 94-97%) at recall \approx 77%. LR and MLP obtained an accuracy of \approx 86-90% with recall in \approx 86% and moderate-high under precision (\approx 69-79%). CNN improved to accuracy \approx 83% and recall \approx 91%, although its precision was quite low (\approx 63%). The selective multi-point balanced dataset S3 gave the best operating metrics. RF, XGB and MLP achieved accuracies \approx 95-96%, $k \approx$ 0.90-0.92 and precision and recall were both around 95%. CNN also improved quite a lot (accuracy \approx 92.5%; $k \approx$ 0.85; precision \approx 89.6%; recall \approx 96.3%). LR was a stable baseline (accuracy \approx 89, $k \approx$ 0.77, precision/recall \approx 88-90%). In S4, accuracy was also high (\approx 94-95% for RF, XGB and MLP; \approx 93% for CNN; \approx 88% for LR), but mostly their optimal thresholds were more permissive than in S3. As a consequence of this, the k values were slightly lower, and the precision-recall trade off was shifted in favor of higher sensitivity.

3.3 Calibration quality

Table 3 shows the post-calibration Brier scores and ECE (10). RF, XGB and MLP performed moderately as indicated by the calibration performance (Brier scores \approx 0.09; ECE \approx 0.065-0.084) in the balanced random dataset, S1-1; while CNN recorded the lowest ECE (0.046), that indicate well-aligned predicted and observed probabilities. In S1-1, LR presented the poorest reliability (Brier 0.111; ECE 0.101), consistent with its tendency to produce overconfident mid-range probabilities in this regime. In S1, Brier scores and ECE values were among the largest across regimes, with CNN and MLP exhibiting the poorest calibration overall (Brier \approx 0.07-0.08; ECE \approx 0.06) although reliability diagrams still revealed overconfident mid-high probability bins. With curated 1:3 design S2, Brier scores generally decreased and ECE often improved for RF, XGB and CNN, whereas LR and MLP retained small residual miscalibration in some bins. Optimal calibration was obtained in the balanced S3 regime. The tree ensembles and MLP achieved low Brier scores (\approx 0.024-0.036), and ECE (10) values (\approx 0.003-0.015), with reliability curves closely following the 45-degree line. CNN also significantly improved (Brier 0.055; ECE 0.010), although its calibration remained less stable than that of XGB and RF. In S4, RF, XGB and MLP yielded Brier \approx 0.03-0.045 and ECE (10) \approx 0.005-0.015, while CNN yielded Brier \approx 0.047 and ECE \approx 0.015.

Generally, isotonic calibration significantly enhanced probability reliability across regimes, and selective/balanced sampling (S3-S4) were associated with the lowest Brier and ECE values, confirming that data design and calibration jointly control the semantic quality of predicted probabilities.

3.4 Map footprints and selectivity

Calibrated probability rasters for each learner and dataset were reclassified into five susceptibility classes via Jenks natural breaks. Class-area percentages within the study-area mask are summarized in Table 4.

Table 3. Post-calibration Brier score and ECE (10) for all models and datasets.

Model	Brier S1-1	Brier S1	Brier S2	Brier S3	Brier S4	ECE S1-1	ECE S1	ECE S2	ECE S3	ECE S4
LR	0.11	0.069	0.078	0.086	0.076	0.101	0.075	0.0727	0.0101	0.008
XGB	0.09	0.082	0.063	0.026	0.031	0.073	0.058	0.068	0.003	0.005
RF	0.09	0.080	0.064	0.036	0.045	0.084	0.060	0.056	0.003	0.007
MLP	0.09	0.082	0.085	0.024	0.036	0.065	0.051	0.072	0.010	0.010
CNN	0.10	0.124	0.072	0.055	0.047	0.046	0.069	0.053	0.010	0.015

Table 4. Class-area percentages (%) for LR, RF, XGB, MLP, and CNN across datasets S1-1, S1–S4 (Jenks five-class LSMs)

Model	Zone	S1-1	S1	S2	S3	S4
LR	Very Low	17.50%	16.40%	12.92%	13.40%	13.50%
	Low	21.50%	20.06%	22.64%	22.88%	25.31%
	Moderate	25.00%	22.22%	27.35%	26.47%	29.60%
	High	23.00%	23.15%	24.79%	25.53%	21.11%
	Very High	13.00%	18.18%	12.30%	11.71%	10.48%
XGB	Very Low	15.00%	14.21%	13.27%	15.47%	21.24%
	Low	22.50%	22.19%	22.65%	20.08%	31.47%
	Moderate	26.00%	26.74%	26.09%	22.43%	22.70%
	High	24.50%	25.65%	25.75%	24.42%	15.73%
	Very High	12.00%	11.21%	12.24%	17.61%	8.86%
RF	Very Low	35.50%	36.79%	37.15%	19.60%	15.67%
	Low	24.00%	23.29%	23.68%	32.65%	28.21%
	Moderate	19.50%	19.01%	18.78%	23.38%	27.93%
	High	14.00%	13.81%	13.39%	16.13%	18.67%
	Very High	7.00%	7.10%	7.00%	8.24%	9.51%
MLP	Very Low	15.00%	14.16%	12.76%	38.62%	15.07%
	Low	25.50%	26.03%	25.48%	23.74%	27.31%
	Moderate	28.00%	28.31%	29.05%	18.25%	28.74%
	High	21.00%	20.85%	21.17%	12.68%	19.16%
	Very High	10.50%	10.65%	11.54%	6.71%	9.71%
CNN	Very_Low	17.00%	15.82%	20.17%	39.20%	15.09%
	Low	24.00%	20.30%	29.82%	23.78%	26.95%
	Moderate	23.00%	22.35%	23.86%	18.16%	28.58%
	High	22.00%	24.17%	16.75%	12.59%	19.42%
	Very High	14.00%	17.36%	9.40%	6.28%	9.96%

The use of the Logistic Regression (LR) generates proportional and graded susceptibility footprint in all datasets. In S1-1-S4, the high percentage of terrain is always taken by the Moderate group ($\approx 22-30\%$), and the High+Very High group covers $\approx 31-36\%$ of the terrain in S1-S3, and 32% in S4. Very Low and Low generally add up to 13-25 per cent and it means that LR does not concentrate the probability mass on extreme classes. Generally, LR is an apparently stable mid-selectivity classifier, whose zoning change across sampling regimes is relatively small.

Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) produces patterns of susceptibility with more contrast, especially in S1-1 and S2 where High+Very High $\approx 36-37\%$ and Very Low+Low $\approx 37-38\%$ respectively. When the prevalence of classes is balanced (S3), the upper-risk footprint grows even larger to 42%, indicating a finer separation. In comparison, the more conservative map is generated by S4 and the

High+Very High is reduced to 25% and the Very Low+Low is already extended to 53%. Therefore, in comparison with LR, XGB is more sensitive to the sampling design, yet stratification between classes is obvious in every regime.

Switching to the Random Forest (RF) decreases the footprint in general. Very Low+Low take up to 59-61% of the area in S1-1 and S2 as compared to High +Very High, which takes up only $\approx 20-21\%$. With S3, the High+Very High category rises slightly to 24%, although the map continues to have a wide base of low risk with a high Low belt. In S4, the upper-risk footprint extends further to 28% with a flourishing Moderate class, giving an equal but manageable priority extent. RF thus yields smaller high-risk areas than XGB but still has significant class distinction.

The Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) leaves the balance a bit more toward higher selectivity as compared to RF. In S1-1 and S2, Low+Moderate

occupies 53-55%, whereas High+Very High occupies 31-33% which is a medium permissive operating profile. With S3, however, the footprint is much more conservative with Very Low growing to 39% with High+Very High growing to 19%. This is in line with better calibration and elevated effective decision thresholds in a balanced sampling. High+Very High in S4 to 29% and Very Low+Low to 42% produce an intermediate pattern.

Lastly, the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) demonstrates the greatest variability in the footprint of all learners. In S1-1-S2, High+Very High represent 36 - 41%, which is higher than the upper-risk stocks of RF and nears XGB. In S3, there is a significant shift in the footprint, as Very Low+Low drops to 63% and High+Very High decreases to 19% which means that there was intense calibration response to 1:1 representation. S4 has an intermediate behavior of High +Very High 29% and Very Low+Low 42%. CNN thus seems to be most susceptible to sampling representativeness and prevalence of classes, which result in broader variability in the susceptibility zoning, compared with the other learners.

Selectivity ratios across models $\frac{High+Very\ High}{Very\ Low+Low}$ maximize in the more permissive regimes (also XGB and CNN under S1-S2) and minimize in conservative or better-calibrated regimes (MLP and CNN under S3) and uniformly across datasets (RF). LR is steadily selective, with moderate selectivity among all datasets and smooth risk stratification, as opposed to sharp class compression. S4 tends to result in intermediate-low selectivity and large Low and Moderate belts, providing a benefit where susceptibility maps will be used as wide screen screening instruments, as opposed to hard and fast prioritization instruments. The revealed S1-1 attachment proves the S1/S2 sampling rule footprints

as being susceptible, interpretable, and internally consistent across learners, especially in the case of LR and XGB.

3.5 Feature importance on the balanced dataset (S3)

Permutation importance on S3 highlighted both model-specific emphases and strong cross-model agreement (Table 5).

LR assigned its largest contributions to Aspect ($\approx 18.9\%$), Slope ($\approx 15.7\%$), and LULC ($\approx 18.5\%$), with TWI ($\approx 11.5\%$) and Soil ($\approx 10.2\%$) also prominent. Roads, Rivers and Faults contributed moderately, while SMI and basin indices (TRI, SPI, Curvature) had smaller effects.

RF ranked Aspect ($\approx 19.3\%$), Slope ($\approx 18.1\%$), Elevation ($\approx 10.4\%$), NDVI ($\approx 9.0\%$) and SMI ($\approx 6.7\%$) among the leading predictors, accompanied by non-negligible contributions from TWI, SPI, Curvature, Roads and Faults.

XGB emphasized SMI ($\approx 26.0\%$), Elevation ($\approx 21.4,3\%$), Slope ($\approx 16.5\%$) and Aspect ($\approx 12.4\%$), with NDVI also important. Roads, Faults and Rivers played secondary roles, while LULC and basin indices contributed little.

MLP highlighted SMI ($\approx 13.1\%$), Elevation ($\approx 16.5\%$), Roads ($\approx 14.1\%$), Rivers ($\approx 9.3\%$) and Aspect ($\approx 10.0\%$), with Slope and NDVI also influential. Soil and LULC were secondary; TRI, TWI, SPI and Curvature were minor.

The CNN strengthened spatial and structural signals: Elevation ($\approx 19.2\%$), SMI ($\approx 20.4\%$), Slope ($\approx 12.4\%$), NDVI ($\approx 10.9\%$), Aspect ($\approx 9.2\%$), Roads ($\approx 9.6\%$), Faults ($\approx 10.8\%$) and Rivers ($\approx 3.2\%$) dominated, while TRI, TWI, SPI, Curvature and LULC contributed very little.

Table 5. Permutation feature importance (%) on S3 for all single models.

Factor	LR	XGBoost	RF	MLP	CNN
Aspect	18.93	12.36	19.25	10.04	9.15
Curvature	1.01	0.58	3.27	0.12	0.25
Elevation	2.03	21.43	10.35	16.46	19.20
Faults	5.23	4.49	4.86	8.43	10.84
LULC	18.54	0.35	5.24	2.79	0.25
NDVI	2.48	7.64	9.02	8.67	10.85
Rivers	2.41	1.64	2.68	9.27	3.21
Roads	2.78	4.60	4.66	14.08	9.59
Slope	15.66	16.51	18.08	7.26	12.36
SMI	2.28	25.98	6.73	13.06	20.43
Soil	10.19	2.11	2.87	5.10	1.92
SPI	4.15	0.40	5.10	1.12	0.56
TRI	2.82	1.61	3.10	2.00	0.81
TWI	11.49	0.31	4.79	1.60	0.57

Despite these differences, all five models converged on a coherent set of dominant controls: relief and exposure (Slope, Aspect, Elevation), anthropogenic and structural factors (Roads, Faults), hydro-surface state (SMI, Rivers), and, to a lesser extent, NDVI and LULC. Basin-scale indices (TRI, TWI, SPI, Curvature) provided only marginal incremental information at 30 m resolution.

4. Discussion

4.1 Sampling design as the primary driver of performance

Among all the learners and measures of evaluation, the sampling design, in particular, the background definition and the LS:NLS ratio, stood out as the predominant control on discrimination, agreement and calibration. With the random 1:3 regime (S1), the majority of the models already obtained high ROC-AUC (>0.93). Nevertheless, the value of k and precision was in the middle range and the optimum probability thresholds were comparatively small meaning that there was a lot of overlap between the LS and NLS scores distributions. In cases where prevalence had been maintained constant, but the NLS background was limited by a ring buffer and an empirically stable terrain mask (S2), k rose systematically, thresholds were shifted upwards, and values of Brier/ECE values had bettered. This represents more reliable probability estimates of similar AUC values and cleaner separation of classes, which points to the fact that the background quality is as important as prevalence. The best effects were recorded within the balanced multi-point design (S3). With a larger LS representation, and combining it with a selective background, all models achieved near-ceiling AUC (0.99 with RF, XGB, and MLP; 0.98 with CNN), as well as k approximately equal to or larger than 0.90 and lowest Brier and ECE scores. The thresholds got conservative, but the recall was very high, which showed that the more representative training distribution, which is also rich, largely removed the usual trade-off between sensitivity and precision. The multi-point unbalanced regime (S4) affirmed that prevalence is still in effect when backgrounds are curated. Discrimination was also high (AUC ≈ 0.98 -0.99), but optimum thresholds were reduced compared to S3 and k was reduced a bit. This is in line with the anticipation that skewed class ratios would be more favourable to permissive cut-points to save recall, even when the background is geologically meaningful. Combined, the difference between S1-S4 shows that NLS sampling that is curated and

terrain matched and sufficient LS representation have a more powerful impact on model faithfulness than style of architecture choice. When the same conditions of design (S2-S3) are met, it becomes possible to have a favourable regime of all learners working, with conservative thresholds, high k and good calibration, and at the same time, map footprints can be interpreted and stable.

4.2 Comparative behaviour of LR, RF, XGB, MLP and CNN

Systematic variations between models were also present within each sampling regime. LR was highly interpretable and had a high ROC-AUC, which is always high (0.94-0.95 in the 1:3 regimes) but k was usually smaller than in case of the nonlinear learners, especially with S3. This behaviour indicates the linear decision boundary, which only takes up the wide predictor-response tendencies but fails to fully benefit the nonlinear association of conditions stimuli. RF and XGB provided the most consistent and overall best k by dataset. Both under S2-S3 obtained high AUC (0.97-0.99) with high agreement and balanced precision-recall, in particular, when fixed thresholds were set by the Youden-J criterion. RF was also generally more conservative and usually more accurate and a little less recalled, but XGB occasionally discovered more LS pixels by a much more costly number of false alarms. MLP performed on a par or slightly better than the tree-based learners in the best data regime (S3), most actually, with k 0.92, almost ceiling AUC, and high-sensitivity footprints that are compact. Nonetheless, with S1-S2, MLP revealed additional variability in k and calibration measures, which is not surprising, because more data and stability is required of neural networks. The short CNN had the greatest reliance on the sampling design. Random 1:3 sampling (S1) gave the smallest k and largest Brier/ECE even with reasonable AUC, suggesting to have unstable and over-confident probabilities. The discrimination and calibration increased significantly under curated and balanced regimes (S2-S3) and the high-susceptibility footprint was more coherent and subdued. This trend indicates that CNN-spatial feature learning brings the greatest value when inventories are large enough and background sampling is properly controlled. In general, RF, XGB, and MLP proved to be the strongest learners in the conditions that are taken into account in this study, and LR offers a clear and stable baseline, and CNN performed best under curated, data-rich conditions.

4.3 From calibrated probabilities to map footprints

The analysis of class areas illustrates how the sampling decisions are conducted between probability scores and actionable susceptibility maps. Throughout S1 and portions of S2 there were learners (outstandingly XGB and CNN) that generated expansive High+Very-High areas (>35-40% of the study area) and somewhat narrow Very-Low foundation. These footprints are applicable to screening of large scale but may overflow verification and mitigation resources in case they are seen as strict priority masks. With S3 the distributions of classes by area were more in line with targeted planning. In the case of the well-calibrated learners, Very-High just usually took a small fraction (6-18%), High was substantial but not dominant, and Very-Low+Low made a broad ground. This has the benefits of producing selective shortlists without increasing the top-rank, representing better and more conservative, better-calibrated thresholds. Patterns in S4 changed to slightly more screening-oriented: Very-Low and Low increased, Moderate did not decrease, and High+Very-High decreased compared to S3. This suggests that class prevalence has an effect not only on classical measures of discrimination, but also on the spatial geometry of LSMs. Notably, the diagnostics of reliability showed consistency with these patterns on a map-level. Low-Brier and ECE (e.g., RF, XGB and MLP with S3) models and datasets generated LSMs with small Very-High cores and wide low-risk bases, and noisier regimes (e.g., S1) inflated intermediate-and high-risk classes. This endorses the suggestion that any susceptibility items that are to be used in planning should be given calibrated probability spaces as well as the explicit reporting of the class-area shares so that end-users can objectively fit the map selectivity to decision context.

4.4 Convergent physical controls from feature importance

Although the architectural differences existed, feature-importance profile came to a shared set of physical controls. Throughout LR, RF, XGB, MLP and CNN, especially in the latter conditions of S3, Slope, Aspect, Elevation, Roads, Faults, SMI and Rivers continued to appear as important predictors. A second tier was comprised of NDVI and LULC and the TRI, TWI, SPI and Curvature did not add much extra data. This agreement is in line with the geomorphology of Sulaymaniyah. The road corridors are one of the means of promoting failure; they

encourage cut-and-fill construction, concentration of drainage, and toe undercutting. Exposure and shear stress is coded in Aspect and Slope, the climatic and lithological gradients are summarised with Elevation, and structural weaknesses and preferred flow paths are coded with Faults. SMI obtures antecedent wetness and adjusts the timing of failures and offers a dynamic proxy of the hydrologic forcing. NDVI and LULC also seem to alter, not to dominate, the susceptibility, some of the signal of which is already available in the form of topography and moisture. Low marginal contributions of TRI, TWI, SPI and Curvature indicate that in cases where there are strong morphometric, structural and wetness controls added, higher-order or basin-scale derivatives do not contribute much new information when working at this resolution. It does not mean the universality of the non-importance of such indices. Instead, it suggests that in such an environment a prediction set with a sparse set of predictors based on topography, structure, moisture and linear corridors can perform well in LSM.

4.5 Implications for operational landslide susceptibility mapping

The findings support several practical recommendations for LSM production:

1. **Prioritize sampling design over model complexity.** Curated, terrain-matched NLS sampling and balanced or near-balanced LS:NLS ratios (when feasible) should be treated as primary design objectives.
2. **Use calibrated probabilities and fixed, documented thresholds.** Isotonic regression markedly improved reliability: thresholds selected on validation data and transferred unchanged to new data provide transparent, reproducible operating points.
3. **Report on both metrics and map footprints.** ROC-AUC and κ should be interpreted alongside Brier/ECE and class-area distributions from Jenks-classified probability rasters, so that statistical performance can be linked directly to expected field workload.
4. **Select models based on robustness and interpretability.** Under data conditions similar to this study, RF, XGB and MLP offer the best balance of discrimination, agreement and reliability, with LR as an interpretable baseline and CNN reserved for curated, data-rich applications.
5. **Exploit convergent feature importance for mitigation.** The shared emphasis on roads,

structural features, steep and aspect-exposed slopes, and wet conditions suggest that corridor stabilization, drainage management, and monitoring of faulted, moisture-prone hillslopes should be central elements of mitigation strategies.

4.6 Limitations and future work

Several limitations should be recognized. First, experiments were conducted in a single mountainous region with specific lithological and climatic characteristics; transferability to other settings remains to be tested explicitly. Second, analyses were based on static inventories and conditioning factors; temporal dynamics of triggers (e.g., rainfall time series) were not modelled. Third, CNN architecture was intentionally kept compact to match data size; more expressive networks might behave differently under larger inventories. Finally, while multiple learners were compared, detailed ensemble strategies are addressed in a separate study.

Future work could extend this framework by: (i) testing transferability in neighboring basins; (ii) incorporating event-based triggers; (iii) exploring deeper CNNs under large inventories; and (iv) evaluating ensembles and domain adaptation strategies.

5. Conclusion

These results suggest that, in this study area, sampling design in particular the definition of the non-landslide backgrounds and the ratio between LS:NLS classes had a stronger influence on performance and map footprints compared to the choice between the learning algorithms evaluated. When non-landslide points were curated using stability masks and multi-point landslide representation with balanced prevalence was adopted, all tested models (LR, RF, XGB, MLP, CNN) achieved excellent discrimination, high κ , good calibration, and selective yet practical susceptibility footprints.

The results emphasize that reliable LSMs for planning in Sulaymaniyah and similar mountainous regions can be obtained by combining careful sampling design with calibrated probabilities and transparent operating thresholds, using robust learners such as RF, XGB or MLP and retaining LR as an interpretable baseline.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Israa Fadhil Ibraheem: Conceptualization; Methodology; Investigation; Data curation; Software; Formal analysis; Validation; Visualization; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing; Project administration.

Mastura Azmi: Supervision; Conceptualization (supporting); Methodology (supporting); Validation (supporting); Writing – review & editing; Resources; Funding acquisition.

Muhammad Wafiy Adli Ramli: Supervision (supporting); Methodology (supporting); Validation (supporting); Visualization (supporting); Writing – review & editing; Resources.

References

- [1] A. U. Ahmad, U. V. Balakrishnan, P. S. Jha, “A Study of Multicollinearity Detection and Rectification under Missing Values”, *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, Vol. 12, No. 1S, pp. 399–418, 2021.
- [2] S. F. Ahmed, M. S. B. Alam, M. Hassan, M. R. Rozbu, T. Ishtiak, N. Rafa, A. H. Gandomi, “Deep Learning Modelling Techniques: Current Progress, Applications, Advantages, and Challenges”, *Artificial Intelligence Review*, Vol. 56, No. 11, pp. 13521–13617, 2023.
- [3] Z. Fang, Y. Wang, C. van Westen, L. Lombardo, “Landslide Hazard Spatiotemporal Prediction Based on Data-Driven Models: Estimating Where, When and How Large Landslides May Be”, *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, Vol. 126, 103631, 2024.
- [4] J. I. Fisher, G. C. Hurtt, R. Q. Thomas, J. Q. Chambers, “Clustered Disturbances Lead to Bias in Large-Scale Estimates Based on Forest Sample Plots”, *Ecology Letters*, Vol. 11, No. 6, pp. 554–563, 2008.
- [5] T. Gu, P. Duan, M. Wang, J. Li, Y. Zhang, “Effects of Non-Landslide Sampling Strategies on Machine Learning Models in Landslide Susceptibility Mapping”, *Scientific Reports*, Vol. 14, No. 1, 7201, 2024.
- [6] F. Huang, H. Xiong, C. Yao, F. Catani, C. Zhou, J. Huang, “Uncertainties of Landslide Susceptibility Prediction Considering Different Landslide Types”, *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, Vol. 15, No. 11, pp. 2954–2972, 2023.
- [7] Y. Huang, C. Zhao, X. Jin, Y. Zhu, M. Peng, Z. Chen, “Case Study of a Landslide Continuous Probability Rainfall Threshold Analysis Based

- on the Prediction Interval Principle”, *Scientific Reports*, Vol. 13, No. 1, 2434, 2023.
- [8] W. Jiang, L. Li, R. Niu, “Impact of Non-Landslide Sample Sampling Strategies and Model Selection on Landslide Susceptibility Mapping”, *Applied Sciences*, Vol. 15, No. 4, 2132, 2025.
- [9] D. E. Kim, J. Liu, S.-Y. Liong, P. Gourbesville, G. Strunz, “Satellite DEM Improvement Using Multispectral Imagery and an Artificial Neural Network”, *Water*, Vol. 13, No. 11, 1551, 2021.
- [10] C. Kumar, G. Walton, P. Santi, C. Luza, “Random Cross-Validation Produces Biased Assessment of Machine Learning Performance in Regional Landslide Susceptibility Prediction”, *Remote Sensing*, Vol. 17, No. 2, 213, 2025.
- [11] A. Mentzafou, A. Papadopoulos, E. Dimitriou, “Flood Generating Mechanisms Investigation and Rainfall Threshold Identification for Regional Flood Early Warning”, *Environmental Earth Sciences*, Vol. 82, No. 10, 242, 2023.
- [12] H. Özvan, O. Şatr, “A Comparative Analysis of Land Use Classification Methods Using Landsat and Ancillary Data in Urban Mapping”, *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, Vol. 11, No. 6, pp. 1–16, 2025.
- [13] N. Rane, S. P. Choudhary, J. Rane, “Ensemble Deep Learning and Machine Learning: Applications, Opportunities, Challenges, and Future Directions”, *Studies in Medical and Health Sciences*, Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 18–41, 2024.
- [14] N. Senaviratna, T. Cooray, “Diagnosing Multicollinearity of Logistic Regression Model”, *Asian Journal of Probability and Statistics*, Vol. 5, No. 2, pp. 1–9, 2019.
- [15] V. K. Sissakian, “The Geology of Erbil and Mahabad Quadrangles, Sheet No. NJ-38-14 and NJ-38-15 (GM5 & GM6)”, *Iraq Geological Survey, Baghdad, Technical Report/Geological Map*, 1998.
- [16] S. Sterlacchini, C. Ballabio, J. Blahut, M. Masetti, A. Sorichetta, “Spatial Agreement of Predicted Patterns in Landslide Susceptibility Maps”, *Geomorphology*, Vol. 125, No. 1, pp. 51–61, 2011.
- [17] T. T. Khoei, H. Ould Slimane, N. Kaabouch, “Deep Learning: Systematic Review, Models, Challenges, and Research Directions”, *Neural Computing and Applications*, Vol. 35, No. 31, pp. 23103–23124, 2023.
- [18] D. J. Varnes, “Landslide Hazard Zonation — A Review of Principles and Practice”, *UNESCO Natural Hazard Series*, 1984.
- [19] Y. Wang, M. Khodadadzadeh, R. Zurita-Milla, “Spatial+: A New Cross-Validation Method to Evaluate Geospatial Machine Learning Models”, *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, Vol. 121, 103364, 2023.
- [20] S. Xu, Y. Song, P. Lu, G. Mu, K. Yang, S. Wang, “An Optimized Non-Landslide Sampling Method for Landslide Susceptibility Evaluation Using Machine Learning Models”, *Natural Hazards*, Vol. 121, No. 5, pp. 5873–5900, 2025.
- [21] J. Zhang, J. Qian, Y. Lu, X. Li, Z. Song, “Study on Landslide Susceptibility Based on Multi-Model Coupling: A Case Study of Sichuan Province, China”, *Sustainability*, Vol. 16, No. 16, 6803, 2024.
- [22] Y. Zhu, D. Sun, H. Wen, Q. Zhang, Q. Ji, C. Li, J. Zhao, “Considering the Effect of Non-Landslide Sample Selection on Landslide Susceptibility Assessment”, *Geomatics, Natural Hazards and Risk*, Vol. 15, No. 1, 2392778, 2024.